

The State of Cloud-Edge-IoT in Europe

CEI-Sphere

part of EU**CloudEdgeIoT**.eu

Deep Dive Analysis and Market Insights

Bridging the Gap: Moving CEI Solutions from Pilot to Production at Scale

The European Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) market is at a critical inflection point. Based on a comprehensive survey of 500 European enterprises across 9 countries, this report uncovers the real commercial needs, operational bottlenecks, and foundational trust mechanisms required to scale CEI architectures

Where We Are: The CEI Adoption Landscape

The Methodology Insights are drawn from decision-makers across four key, operationally critical industries:

Manufacturing

27,6%

**Energy
& Utilities**

25,2%

**Transportation
& Logistics**

26,2%

Resources

21%

Adoption is advancing, but unevenly. While data collection technologies are largely solved, distributing intelligence closer to physical assets remains a work in progress

IoT is Mature

The vast majority of companies are using IoT technologies extensively across all surveyed industries.

**AI/ML
is Expanding**

Usage is widespread, with AI-driven predictive maintenance standing out as a high-priority capability to reduce downtime and extend asset life.

**Edge Computing
is Emerging**

Only 3.8% of organisations report extensive edge usage today. However, massive growth is on the horizon, with 36.0% planning to adopt it within the next 24 months

What's Holding Us Back?

The greatest friction in CEI adoption is not at the device level, but in the layers that connect, orchestrate, and govern these complex distributed systems.

- **Integration & Interoperability:** Integrating CEI with existing IT/OT systems remains a key challenge.
- **Skills Gap:** Shortages in edge architecture, AI/ML, and cybersecurity slow adoption.
- **Data & Security:** Device vulnerabilities and complex data governance across partners create additional barriers.

When transitioning from pilot to production, buyers select CEI vendors based on risk reduction, not just upfront cost. The main criteria for vendor selection include:

1. Integration with existing IT/OT systems.
2. Security and compliance readiness.
3. Support for open standards and interoperability

Building Trust to Scale

The Power of a CEI Trust Label As CEI solutions scale across distributed environments, trust becomes the ultimate currency. To combat fragmentation and unclear vendor capabilities, the market is demanding verification

Key features desired in a trust label include verification of standards compliance, data sovereignty/security assurances, and certification of orchestration capabilities

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